

Executive Functions and Emotional Regulation in Autism Spectrum Disorder: Clinical Implications

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Abstract

Cognitive neuroscience has shown that the development of emotional regulation is closely linked to several basic executive functions, such as attention control, inhibition of inappropriate behaviour and decision-making, all of which are activated in emotionally demanding situations [95,101]. Executive functions (EF) are, in fact, a fundamental element of self-regulation, defined as the ability to regulate cognition, emotions and behaviour [19,55]. In people with autism spectrum disorder (ASD), deficits in EF are frequently observed. They are related to difficulties such as theory of mind, social cognition, and repetitive and restricted behaviour patterns, which negatively affect the quality of life (Pugliese et al., 2015). Furthermore, these difficulties in EF can compromise social skills, mainly regulating behaviour in social contexts. Despite numerous studies, the role of EF in ASD is still unclear, with conflicting results due to factors such as age, functioning profile, comorbidities (e.g. ADHD) and assessment methodologies used [33]. The identification of an executive dysfunction profile through neuropsychological assessment, together with targeted interventions to enhance executive functions, could not only improve the understanding of the neural mechanisms underlying ASD but also offer new opportunities to promote better emotional regulation and to improve diagnosis, assessment and clinical treatment.

Introduction

Autism spectrum disorder (ASD) encompasses a heterogeneous set of persistent neurodevelopmental disorders that manifest in early childhood [1]. Although genetic and neurobiological factors contribute significantly to the ASD phenotype, cognitive functions, mainly executive functions (EF), play a crucial role in the characteristic behaviours of ASD. [74] describe the abilities that make-up EFs as behaviours such as planning, impulse control, inhibition of overbearing but irrelevant responses, goal maintenance, organised search, and flexibility of thought and action. Executive Functions (EF) are often defined as a network of higher-order cognitive processes that involve directing or coordinating other lower-order psychological processes to achieve certain goals [2,34]. Therefore, executive functions are psychological processes fundamental to the self-regulation of thoughts, behaviour, and emotions in everyday life.

More Information

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Since the 1990s, research has shown that deficits in EFs are frequently found in people with autism spectrum disorders: they have long been a focus of interest as they contribute to specific impairments in the areas of theory of mind and social cognition, restricted and repetitive patterns of behaviour, as well as for their broader impacts on the quality of life of people with autism. Difficulties in these functions can also account for impairments in social skills, specifically to context-dependent regulation of one's behaviour [77]. Several studies have analysed the difficulties of people with ASD (Autism Spectrum Disorder) about EF functioning, specifically:

Inhibition. Inhibitory control concerns suppressing inappropriate behaviour and regulating behaviour according to circumstances. People with ASD have difficulties in this area, which manifest themselves in social and communicative interactions and are related to the repetitive behaviours typical of ASD. Studies

have shown lower performance in tasks requiring inhibition, with particular difficulties in inhibiting predominant responses [42,60].

Cognitive flexibility is the ability to adapt to changes and switch between tasks. People with ASD tend to exhibit behavioural rigidity and resistance to change. Tests such as the Wisconsin Card Sorting Test (WCST) have shown that children with ASD make more perseveration errors, demonstrating difficulty changing the categorisation criterion. Measures with ecological validity, such as the Behavior Rating Inventory of Executive Function (BRIEF), were sensitive in distinguishing between children with and without ASD [61].

Planning involves the ability to organise and monitor sequences of activities. Children with ASD show clear difficulties in this area compared to peers with typical development and those with ADHD. Some longitudinal studies have shown that adolescents with ASD do not improve in planning processes over time [41].

Working memory is crucial for reasoning and learning. People with ASD have difficulties updating working memory, which is reflected in lower test performance. Studies have also shown significant difficulties in the visuospatial and verbal components of working memory, with slower response times than in control groups [52,63].

The Link between Executive Functions and Emotional Regulation in ASD

Cognitive neuroscience has shown that emotional regulation (RE) development is influenced by FEs, such as attention control, inhibition of inappropriate behaviour and decision-making, particularly in emotionally challenging situations [95,101]. FE is part of self-regulation, which includes the management of cognition, emotions and behaviour [19,55]. Difficulty in emotional regulation leads to increased intensity of emotions and difficulty in recovering from a negative emotional state.

Studies have shown that children with low FE skills have more incredible difficulty in emotional regulation, with frequent expressions of negative emotions and tendencies towards impulsive behaviour [92]. Emotional competence, which implies the ability to manage one's and others' emotions, is crucial in this context, and the flexibility of EFs is crucial for dealing with socially appropriate emotional situations [84].

They are divided into 'cool' (cognitive) and 'hot' (emotional-social). The former refer to metacognitive functions, related to attentional control and behaviour, while the latter are related to managing emotions and social decisions [101]. Difficulties in Emotional Regulation (ER) in children and adults with ASD are manifested by intense emotional reactions, difficulties in switching between emotions and controlling emotional responses [68,99].

Recent studies suggest that difficulty in emotional regulation may be an inherent feature of ASD, with research supporting this hypothesis [58,71,88]. In general, children with ASD may have significant problems in using emotional regulation strategies and managing emotions, affecting their mental health and social interactions [3]. ER is crucial for socialisation, as positive and negative emotional reactions need to be handled in social contexts such as school to adapt to norms and goals. However, individuals with ASD tend to overreact to emotional stimuli without a specific purpose, using fewer adaptive RE strategies and showing a maladaptive pattern in the use of these strategies, such as emotional suppression, resignation and avoidance [50,86]. This is linked to reduced cognitive flexibility and difficulties in modulating behaviour [10].

ER impairment is also associated with co-occurring psychopathologies such as anxiety, depression, and suicide risk [4,25,28], and with negative outcomes in social, academic, and quality of life [49].

Studies on executive and ER functions suggest that difficulties with shifting attention, planning, and working memory, which are impaired in ASD [73,81], contribute to difficulties in emotional regulation [70]. In particular, problems with working memory and rumination are linked to difficulty flexibly regulating emotions [72]. Neurological observations show that overlapping brain regions, such as the prefrontal cortex and the amygdala, support emotional regulation and executive functions. These areas are activated during tasks involving attention, cognitive flexibility, response inhibition and working memory. However, in individuals with ASD, atypical brain activation patterns are observed during EF-related tasks, suggesting deficits in cognitive reappraisal and emotion regulation [76,80]. Furthermore, reduced connectivity between frontal regions and the limbic system has been found in individuals with ASD, with fewer prefrontal areas and amygdala involvement during emotion down-regulation [87].

Longitudinal studies have shown that alterations in EF components, such as inhibition and cognitive flexibility, are predictive of later psychiatric symptoms, such as anxiety and depression [27,96]. Specifically, difficulties in cognitive flexibility are correlated with depression, whereas difficulties in inhibition are associated with emotional regulation but not directly with symptoms of anxiety or depression.

Since emotion regulation and executive functions appear to be correlated with various outcomes, interventions directly targeting these abilities could be particularly effective.

Similar to the increasing adoption of transdiagnostic treatments for mood and anxiety disorders in neurotypical populations, which focus on emotion

regulation [4,12,36], interventions targeting executive functions have shown efficacy in ASD. One of the most studied programmes in this area is 'Unstuck and On Target' [57], a transdiagnostic group intervention applied in school and clinical settings. This program also involves parents through different levels of training and participation and is associated with improvements in cognitive flexibility and problem-solving and ER-related measures [37,56]. The results suggest that jointly examining RE and FE may be particularly useful in assessing their relationships with anxiety and depression [4].

Impaired executive functions are linked to social and emotional problems in ASD, and metacognition, i.e. awareness and monitoring of one's cognitive processes, plays a key role in their development. Metacognitive training has also improved EF skills in children with ASD [45]. Studies such as that of [96] have shown that difficulties in EF, observed from childhood, predict long-term social, emotional and behavioural problems in young people with ASD, demonstrating the importance of addressing executive difficulties to improve overall outcomes. [62] showed a relationship between executive processes of behavioural regulation (inhibition, displacement and emotional control) and social functioning, observed in both typical children and those with ASD. However, the relationship between the social symptoms of ASD and metacognitive executive functions (such as planning, working memory and monitoring) was distinct and not present in the typical population [5]. Stronger metacognitive abilities were associated with fewer autistic social symptoms, suggesting that social difficulties in ASD are primarily related to specific components of Efs [5].

Although difficulties in executive functions appear to decrease with age, studies have shown that they persist in daily life in youth and adults with ASD, suggesting that progress in these functions is impaired, making it difficult to adapt to increasing environmental demands. Daily difficulties in ASD are predictive of emotional, behavioural and social symptoms in young people with ASD. These findings suggest that early interventions on FE, combined with psychosocial therapies, could prevent or mitigate future social and emotional problems in children with ASD.

The connection between executive functions and emotional regulation can be bidirectional. To adopt effective ER strategies, individuals must manage strategy choice, switch easily between options, and apply the necessary steps, a process that requires working memory, cognitive flexibility, and planning. In contrast, tasks that require EF, such as school activities or specific goals, can generate stress and negatively affect performance [49]. Other studies support this relationship: in the meta-analysis by [32], a link between EF, ER and affective problems is reported. For

example, a study by Jahromi et al. on preschool children with ASD found that these children show shorter delayed gratification than typical peers and adopt temptation-focused strategies more frequently. ER was strongly associated with using these strategies, suggesting that the ability to delay gratification involves the management of intense emotions. A study by [79] examined cognitive difficulties in children with ASD and ADHD, finding that cognitive inflexibility in children with ASD was correlated with higher levels of anxiety and depression, while children with ADHD showed difficulties with inhibition and aggressive behaviour. Inflexibility and disinhibition have been identified as crucial factors in both disorders. Other studies have explored the link between executive functions and emotional symptoms in children with ASD [3]. [75] found that cognitive inflexibility predicted externalising symptoms and emotional problems, influencing ASD symptoms and behaviour.

[82] suggested that brain organisation influences cognitive and behavioural difficulties in children with ASD, with emotional control associated with inhibition and shifting. [11] found no associations between EF and emotional symptoms in children with high-functioning autism, while [39] observed that EF mediated the relationship between sensory processing and behavioural problems.

In conclusion, emotional dysregulation is closely related to difficulties in EFs in children with ASD. Clinical interventions should improve EFs, such as inhibition, shifting, working memory and metacognition, to promote better emotional regulation and reduce maladaptive behaviour, with potential long-term social and emotional benefits.

Measuring EF: Profiles and Assessment Protocols

Among the primary tests to assess the different domains of FE and the emotional competence of children and adolescents with ASD, the following are the most widely used:

- *Wisconsin Card Sorting Test* [61]: the WCST measures the ability to change cognitive strategy in response to feedback, assessing mental flexibility and inhibition. It is generally administered to individuals aged 16 and into adulthood.

- *Tower of London* [87] primarily requires inhibitory skills and planning. The test measures the ability to plan and organise the actions necessary to achieve a goal by requiring participants to move a certain number of discs between bars to replicate a target configuration. It is mainly administered to individuals from 6-7 years old up to adults, making it suitable for a wide range of ages. The Tower of London is a valuable tool for assessing planning and problem-solving skills, with applications in clinical and research contexts.

- *Stroop Test* [66], which assesses inhibitory control.

- *'Test delle Ranette'*, which is based on the Walk-Don't Walk of [65], is used to assess inhibition; it consists of 20 scales (plus 2 test scales) on each of which a small frog is drawn. The child's task is to cross the frog every time a certain sound called 'GO' is presented and to stop every time another sound called 'STOP' appears [66].

- *Hayling & Brixton Test* consists of 20 sentences in which the final word is absent. The sentences are divided into two groups (A-L; 1-10); the child has to complete with a correct word (sentence A-L) or has to provide an alternative word that is not semantically related to the sentence and the correct answer (sentences 1-10) [20].

- *Matching Familiar Figure Test* [51,53] or the *'statue' and 'response set' tasks* (Mahone et al., 2006) help identify children who have difficulties with response inhibition, while tests based on the flanker paradigm [17,26] are used to assess interference control.

- *Behavior Rating Inventory of Executive Function* [44]: this is a widely used questionnaire to assess difficulties in EF and appears to be the measure with the most clinical sensitivity in differentiating children with ASD from those with typical development [33].

- *Behavioral Assessment of the Dysexecutive Syndrome* [97]: The BADS consists of six subtests and a self-assessment questionnaire. Each subtest is designed to measure a specific aspect of executive functions. The BADS is primarily intended for adults but can also be administered to older adolescents, especially if there is a need to assess executive functions in a clinical or educational context.

- *Cambridge Neuropsychological Test Automated Battery* (CANTAB) is a computerised test battery designed to assess a wide range of cognitive functions, including executive functions. It is designed to be administered to individuals from 6 to adulthood.

- *Inhibition and Animal Sorting of the NEUROPSYCHOLOGICAL ASSESSMENT, Second Edition (NEPSY-II)*: NEPSY is a neuropsychological test battery designed to assess various cognitive functions in children and adolescents. NEPSY-II is intended for children and adolescents between 3 and 16 years old. The Inhibition and Animal Sorting subtests assess cognitive flexibility in children and adolescents.

- *Trail Making Test* [78]: The test consists of two parts. Part A assesses cognitive processing speed, and Part B measures cognitive flexibility and alternating attention [6]. There are also adapted versions of the TMT, including the DKEFS and the children's version of the TMT-B [6].

As far as the neuropsychological assessment of executive functions in *adults* is concerned, it is based on various tests, some of which are used regularly while others are used less frequently. Among those most frequently used are:

- *Frontal Assessment Battery* (FAB) is a short battery comprising six sub-tests: similarity conceptualisation, lexical fluency by phonemic modality, motor programming (Luria series), response to conflicting instructions, go-no-go task, and prehension behaviour. Each test has a score ranging from 0 to 3 (total score range 0-18; administration time approximately 10 minutes) [35].

- *Stroop Test* for assessing inhibitory control.

- *Phonemic and Semantic Fluency*: A linguistic test assessing lexical access and mental flexibility [31].

- *Modified five-point test*, a test that evaluates the patient's 'unique designs' and 'designs with strategy' by assessing their cognitive flexibility.

- *Visual Search*, a number-cancelling test designed to investigate selective attention [91].

- *Verbal Reasoning Test*: a neuropsychological instrument to assess verbal reasoning, comprehension and critical thinking skills.

- *Cognitive Estimation Task* (CET), a test that assesses the ability to select and regulate cognitive planning processes, uses estimation judgments [90].

- *Rey-Osterrieth Complex Figure*, where the figure production approach is assessed, considering the fragmentation of the elements that make-up the figure and planning [22].

Clock Drawing Test: This test measures skills such as planning, memory, and visual-spatial ability [21].

Tests assessing emotions and emotional regulation include:

- *Beck Anxiety Inventory* [13] is a self-assessment instrument designed to measure the severity of anxiety. The BAI is primarily intended for individuals aged 17 years or older. However, it can also be administered to younger adolescents (13 years and older) with appropriate supervision by a mental health professional.

- *Beck Depression Inventory, Second Edition* [14]: is one of the most widely used self-assessment questionnaires to measure the severity of depression. The BDI-II is primarily intended for individuals aged 13 years or older [7]. It is widely used in clinical and research settings for adolescents and adults [7].

- *Difficulties in Emotion Regulation Scale* [47]: is a self-assessment instrument used to measure difficulties in emotion regulation. Initially developed for adults, the DERS was later adapted for adolescents and older children (from 8 years of age).

Identifying a cognitive profile with executive dysfunction could better clarify the neural circuits associated with ASD and improve diagnosis, treatment and therapeutic options. This investigation sheds light on a fundamental aspect in education and psychology: the relationship between executive functions, emotional dysregulation, and affective problems. Understanding these links is essential to delving into

the mechanisms underlying the emotional regulation difficulties found in children and adolescents with autism spectrum disorder.

Methodology

The intervention for the improvement of emotional control and behavioural crisis management consists of a structured, progressive process aimed at enhancing the patient's emotional self-regulation skills (Fig. 1). The first step is the assessment of self-regulation, a crucial aspect to understand whether the subject can manage his or her emotions effectively. If the level of emotional self-regulation is insufficient, a specific programme is started to develop this competence. If, on the other hand, control is already fair but not yet optimal, areas in need of improvement are identified, focusing in particular on practical strategies such as teaching self-regulation through inhibitory control techniques and the use of daily organisation tools. At this stage, *parental training* is also provided to ensure that family members are involved in the process and can support the patient in transferring the acquired skills into the everyday context. If progress is partial, further strategies are implemented by repeating the teaching cycle and regularly monitoring the self-regulation score. When the patient's emotional control reaches an adequate level, the intervention process continues with the analysis of *coping skills*, i.e. the subject's ability to cope with stress and difficult situations.

If deficiencies are found in this area, a targeted programme is introduced to strengthen problem-solving skills, emotional self-regulation and emotion management through strategies such as positive thinking, problem-solving and mindfulness techniques. Once coping skills are enhanced, it is checked whether the patient can apply them effectively, continuing to monitor and refine their skills.

In parallel, overall *emotional regulation* is investigated, an essential aspect to ensure that the patient controls emotions in the present moment and modulates them appropriately in situations of stress or change. In the event of difficulties in this area, we intervene with a programme that focuses on strengthening executive functions, such as cognitive flexibility and working memory [8], which are crucial for managing emotions dynamically and adaptively. This approach enables the patient to cope better with daily changes and challenges, thus improving his or her self-regulation in the long term.

In addition to individual skills, the *context* (environment) in which the patient lives plays a key role

in the intervention process. External stimuli, such as a sensory-overloaded environment or problematic social dynamics, can negatively influence emotional regulation. Therefore, it is essential to identify and manage these factors, creating an environment that promotes calm and well-being. In the case of difficulties due to contextual factors, action is taken by creating more structured and supportive contexts that can reduce stress and improve the patient's ability to self-regulate.

Finally, functional skills, such as communicating, solving problems, and adapting to daily routines, should not be overlooked. Suppose the patient presents difficulties in these areas. In that case, a further specific intervention is initiated to improve communication, social, and organisational skills to foster greater autonomy and reduce the risk of emotional frustration.

In summary, the intervention to improve emotional regulation and behavioural crisis management is an integrated process combining continuous assessment and targeted interventions on self-regulation, coping skills, emotional regulation, contextual factors, and functional skills. This approach allows emotional and behavioural difficulties to be comprehensively addressed, promoting balanced emotion management and lasting well-being.

An example of an easy-to-administer instrument designed to measure and monitor a person's level of self-regulation in different situations is shown in Tab. 1, with a focus on the ability to manage emotions, perseverance in the face of difficulties and adaptation to circumstances [48]. Each item on the list, from '*Accepts interference from others during a pleasurable activity*' to '*Relaxes if feeling tense, tired or agitated*', explores specific aspects of self-regulation, such as tolerance of frustration, ability to concentrate despite distractions, acceptance of delays, emotional management and persistence in completing tasks. Each behaviour is rated on a scale of 0 to 3, which allows for a score based on the frequency or intensity with which the observed behaviour occurs. Scores < 50 represent poor self-regulation, scores between 51-79 represent sufficient self-regulation and scores > 80 represent excellent self-regulation to be maintained over time.

This tool is handy for educators, psychologists, and other professionals who wish to objectively and precisely assess self-regulation skills to develop targeted interventions and customised support strategies. Ultimately, it offers valuable support in analysing behaviour and designing individual growth and development paths.

Figure 1: Descriptive Flow Chart Relating to the Intervention on Executive Functions (EF) and Emotional Regulation (ER)

Coping Skills refers to the cognitive and behavioural strategies each person uses to face specific external or internal challenges perceived as being beyond their resources [60]. Emotional Regulation includes how individuals modulate their emotions in response to internal or external situations. These processes can be either conscious or unconscious and involve a series of strategies that allow the modulation of the intensity, duration and type of emotion experienced. Contextual Factors include the environmental and situational variables influencing an individual's behaviour. Identifying and modifying these factors reduces the risk of behavioural crises since environmental conditions can play a significant role in the onset and management of such crises. Functional Skills include those essential

for a person's autonomy and daily well-being, such as self-care and domestic skills, enabling the individual to interact effectively with the environment [8] it, satisfy their needs and actively participate in social life. Finally, Physical Illness is any physical condition that causes discomfort or pain and can significantly and negatively influence the user's behaviour.

Emotional Self-Regulation Scale (ESS)

Instructions. The Emotional Self-Regulation Scale (ESS) rating is expressed with four scores: 0 corresponds to 'never' emitted behaviour; 1 corresponds to 'sporadically' emitted behaviour; 2 corresponds to 'sometimes' emitted behaviour; 3 corresponds to 'always' emitted behaviour.

Table 1: Emotional Self-Regulation Scale (ESS)

01) Accepts the 'interference' of others during a pleasurable activity.	0	1	2	3
02) Performs what is asked of him and completes it.	0	1	2	3
03) Carries out a task for at least 10' even in the presence of disturbances or distractions.	0	1	2	3
04) Changes activity, if asked, without protesting (crying, self- or hetero aggressiveness, etc.).	0	1	2	3
05) Easily adapts to new situations.	0	1	2	3
06) Controls his emotionality without emitting maladaptive behaviour (stereotypies, compulsivity, etc.).	0	1	2	3
07) Spends at least two minutes analysing a new task before starting it.	0	1	2	3
08) Corrects his performance errors without getting angry.	0	1	2	3
09) Tolerates frustrating situations (failures, taking away a game, scolding, etc.).	0	1	2	3
10) Persists in a task, to the point of finishing it, even if he encounters difficulties.	0	1	2	3
11) Accepts delays (at least 3 minutes) in the delivery of what he wishes to have as soon as possible.	0	1	2	3
12) Relaxes (listens to music, lies down on the bed, etc.) if he feels tense, tired or agitated.	0	1	2	3

Table 2: The Sum Transcribed in the Square with the Highlighted Sides of the Emotional Self-Regulation Scale (ESS)

SELF-REGULATION [DoS = (PO/36) x 100]					
Environments	OS		MOS	DoS	
	Sep-24	Mar-25		Sep-24	Mar-25
Home with Therapist (HT)	19	25	36	51	69
Home with Parents (HP)	5	9		14	25
Clinic Center with Therapist (CC)	22	28		61	78
Other:					

Tab. 2 - The sum transcribed in the square with the highlighted sides of the Emotional Self-Regulation Scale (ESS) is reported in the 'OS' (Obtained Score) column and then divided by 36 (MOS: Maximum Obtainable Score) and multiplied by 100, the result is transcribed in the 'DoS' (Degree of Self-Regulation) column, which is expressed with 4 'judgements': 'EXCELLENT' if the score is 80% or higher (must be maintained over time), 'SUFFICIENT' if it is between 51% and 79% (must be improved to 80%), 'POOR' if it is between 25% and 49% (must be enhanced to reach the next cut-offs) and 'INEXISTENT' below 25% (must be entirely taught). The final DoS score is always calculated by averaging the scores in the contexts where the assessment was made (Fig. 5) [9].

Clinical Case

A. is a 28-year-old man diagnosed with autism spectrum disorder with a mild-medium functioning profile, assessed through the 'Questionnaire for the Identification of Functioning Profile' (IFP) [9]. The parents report significant difficulties in their son's emotional regulation, characterised by a high sensitivity to daily frustrations, with episodes of irritability and aggressiveness in response to stressful or unexpected situations. Specifically, the boy shows marked difficulty in managing his emotions, with

explosive reactions that include crying, screaming or aggressive behaviour towards himself or others. His autonomy in daily activities is limited: he needs constant support to perform basic tasks such as dressing, eating or organising his space. On completing the self-regulation form in the family context with his parents, he scored 14 (September 2024), thus falling within the range of scores indicating poor self-regulation and needing targeted interventions to improve emotional management and behavioural regulation.

Intervention

A cognitive function assessment was carried out to explore A.'s overall cognitive functioning using a neuropsychological battery to investigate memory, attention, and executive functions. The tests administered included the MOCA, the RAVLT, the Story Memory, the Verbal Span, the Rey-Osterrieth Complex Figure, the Phonemic and Semantic Fluency, the Trail Making Test and the Stroop Test. The results showed the presence of polysectorial difficulties, with a pronounced impairment in executive functions mainly characterised by difficulties in inhibitory control, mental flexibility, attention and working memory (Tab. 2).

The intervention plan was structured to address A.'s main areas of difficulty with executive functions, mainly inhibitory control and visual and verbal memory. The proposed exercises aim to develop and strengthen specific cognitive skills through a gradual and targeted approach.

For **inhibitory control**, an exercise was proposed in which A. had to perform two tasks: clap his hands each time he saw a picture of an animal and, conversely, name letters that were shown randomly. This exercise aimed to stimulate selective attention and manage interference between the two tasks so that the patient learnt to inhibit irrelevant automatic responses and focus on relevant cues. The percentage of errors made during the sessions was considered for data collection. An exercise was proposed to reinforce visual memory in which A. observed a series of coloured, categorically unrelated images. After a short exposure period, the images were darkened, and the patient had to remember what he had seen. This exercise focused on the patient's ability to store visual information quickly and improve his ability to retrieve visual information at a distance. A further exercise focused on **verbal memory**, in which a series of words were read, and the patient had to recall them afterwards.

Both memory tasks were initially simplified, using only three pictures and three words, which aligned with A.'s basic skill level. Subsequently, the number of pictures and words was increased to 4 to stimulate his ability to store and retrieve information progressively. The percentages of correct answers over the number of sessions were measured for both tasks.

For each exercise, **behavioural strategies** were applied, such as error correction, which allowed the patient to recognise and correct any incorrect answers in real time, and **shaping**, which facilitated the gradual acquisition of the required skills, reinforcing progress in small steps. These activities were repeated and adapted throughout the intervention, constantly monitoring the patient's progress to make the intervention as effective as possible.

After the cognitive training, the self-regulation form was recompiled, assessing A.'s behaviour in three specific contexts: at home with his parents, at home with the therapist and at the clinical centre with the therapists.

Results

The cognitive enhancement work led to a progressive improvement in visual memory, verbal memory and executive functions. In particular, executive function training showed significant progress. In the baseline phase, A. made 17.5% of errors in the inhibitory control task. During the intervention phase, a steady reduction in errors was observed until the complete absence of errors was achieved, which was also maintained over time (Fig. 2).

Regarding the verbal and visual memory tasks, initially, A. could not remember four stimuli correctly during the baseline phase. However, throughout the intervention, the percentage of correct answers gradually increased to an accuracy of 90%, a value that was also maintained in the maintenance phase (Figs. 3 and 4).

Figure 2: The Graph Illustrates the Trend in the Percentage of Errors Committed by A. in the Inhibitory Control Task, Comparing the Baseline (A) with the Intervention Phase (B)

In phase A, the subject presents a high error rate of 17.5%, indicating difficulties in impulse management and inhibitory control. However, during phase B, in which the intervention was introduced, a progressive error reduction is observed, with error-free performance achieved at the intervention's end. This improvement is maintained over time, indicating a stabilisation of the progress achieved and a consolidation of the skills acquired.

Figure 3: The Graph Illustrates the Development of A.'s Percentage of Correct Answers in Visual Memory Task Involving the Recall of Four Images. The Graph Compares the Basal Phase (A) with the Intervention Phase (B)

In phase A, the subject cannot provide correct answers, showing difficulties retrieving visual information. However, during phase B, with the introduction of the intervention, a significant performance improvement is

observed, with a progressive increase in the percentage of correct answers, reaching 90% at the end of the treatment period. This improvement suggests enhancing visual memory skills, which were maintained over time, indicating a consolidation of the skills acquired during the maintenance phase.

Table 3: Comparison between the Raw Scores Obtained During the Baseline Phase and Those Recorded at a Follow-Up after Six Months

Test	Raw Scores Baseline	Raw Scores Follow up
MoCA	6	12
RAVLT (immediate Recall)	15	33
RAVLT (Delayed Recall)	0	4
Story Memory	0	10
Verbal Span	3	4
Rey-Osterrieth Complex Figure	10,5	11
Rey-Osterrieth Complex Figure (Delayed Recall)	1	4
Phonemic Fluency	6	10
Semantic Fluency	20	25
Trail Making Test (A)	160	95
Stroop Test (Time Interference)	40	20
Stroop Test (Error Interference)	5	0

The results show improvement in various cognitive domains, including increased verbal span, the number of words recalled in the RAVTL, story memory, attention, spatial exploration (assessed by the Trail Making Test) and inhibitory control (measured by the Stroop Test).

Figure 4: The Graph Shows the Development of A.'s Percentage of Correct Answers in Verbal Memory Tasks Involving Recalling Four Verbal Items. The Graph Compares the Basal Phase (A) with the Intervention Phase (B)

In phase A, the subject cannot provide correct answers, indicating initial difficulties in word retrieval. However, in phase B, a significant improvement in the percentage of correct answers is observed, with a progressive increase in performance up to 90% of correct answers at the end of the intervention period. This improvement suggests enhancing verbal memory skills, which were consolidated over time and maintained during the maintenance phase, demonstrating the durability of the acquired progress.

After six months of intervention, A.'s degree of self-regulation was assessed in different contexts. In the context of 'home with therapists' (HT), the score was 69, while in 'centre with therapists (CC)', the score rose to 77, both in the range of sufficient self-regulation. The self-regulation form was also completed in the context of 'home with parents' (HP), where there was an improvement in the score. However, the result remains in the poor self-regulation range. This outcome could be attributed to the lack of active participation of family members, who refused to continue to be involved in *parent coaching*. This emphasises the importance of a constant commitment on the part of all the caregivers to ensure the generalisation of the progress achieved during the intervention in the various contexts of daily life.

Figure 5: The Graph Shows A.'s Self-Regulation Scores in the Different Assessment Contexts: Home with Parents (HP), Home with Therapists (HT) and Centre with Therapists (CC)

The bars indicate the scores obtained in each context, comparing the different environments and times: September 2024 (Baseline) and March 2025 (follow-up). In the HT context, A. obtained a score of 69, placing him in the range of sufficient self-regulation; in CC, he obtained a score of 77, also in the range of sufficiency, while in the HP context, despite an improvement compared to the initial phase, the score remains lower, indicating a situation of poor self-regulation.

Discussion

The results of the present study indicate that cognitive training positively impacted A.'s cognitive abilities, with significant improvements in executive functions, visual and verbal memory, and inhibitory control. The intervention proved effective in improving the subject's ability to reduce errors in the inhibitory control task, leading to the absence of errors in the final phase, with a result that was maintained in the long term. This improvement in executive functions is particularly relevant since inhibitory control is a fundamental skill for self-regulation and daily functioning.

The data show a significant increase in verbal and visual memory performance, going from complete difficulty retrieving information during the baseline to 90% accuracy in the final stages of the intervention. This suggests that, in addition to improving specific memory skills, the intervention positively affected working memory and the ability to retrieve information, essential skills for autonomy in daily life.

However, the analysis of the results highlighted some discrepancies between the various evaluation contexts. While the scores obtained in the therapeutic context (both at home with the therapist and at the centre with the therapists) indicated sufficient self-control, the results in the family context (home with the parents) showed an improvement but did not reach a sufficient level. This difference between therapeutic and family contexts can be attributed to parents' lack of active participation in the parent coaching programme, which limited the possibility of transferring cognitive and behavioural improvements to the family environment. The low participation of family members deserves particular attention. The generalisation of results, i.e., the ability to apply the skills learned in therapeutic contexts to everyday life, is a crucial aspect of the success of any intervention. The active involvement of family members is fundamental to reinforcing and maintaining progress, contributing to an adequate integration of skills in the patient's daily life.

Furthermore, the results suggest that the integrated approach, including traditional measurements and direct observations, provided a complete and more precise view of A.'s cognitive and behavioural abilities. Monitoring performance in real situations and contextualised analysis made it possible to see improvements in task performance and the patient's daily life, highlighting an increase in the ability to control oneself and adapt to environmental demands. These results highlight the importance of a multifocal and personalised approach, which considers the variety of contexts in which the patient finds himself and the different support figures involved in the therapeutic process. Although the intervention successfully improved cognitive functions, it showed that lasting and generalised change requires a continuous and joint

commitment between professionals and family members.

Conclusions

In conclusion, the intervention improved A.'s cognitive abilities, particularly in executive functions, visual and verbal memory, and inhibitory control, as revealed by the follow-up evaluation. These results highlight the effectiveness of the cognitive enhancement programme in improving A.'s ability to manage and regulate his behaviour, with concrete progress that has been maintained over the long term. The progress in cognitive performance and impulse control translated into an increase in self-control, as evidenced by the DoS score (Degree of Self-control) six months after the intervention.

However, the evaluation of the results also showed differences in the various contexts. While the progress made in therapeutic contexts (both at home with therapists and at the centre) was promising, the scores in the family context were less satisfactory, suggesting the need for more active and constant involvement by family members in the intervention process. This highlights the importance of a global approach that is not limited to the therapeutic environment alone but also actively involves the family to favour the generalisation of results in everyday situations.

Despite the positive results, the present study has some limitations that need to be taken into account. First, the reference sample consists of a single case, which limits the generalisability of the results. Future research should include larger samples to allow for more evident conclusions about the effectiveness of the intervention. Furthermore, the relatively short duration of the intervention (6 months) and the evaluation of the results over a limited period of time may not be sufficient to assess the long-term effects of the cognitive enhancement program. The effectiveness of the treatment could evolve over time, and a more extensive follow-up would allow for a better understanding of the durability of the improvements obtained.

Another limitation concerns the involvement of the family, which in A.'s case was not as continuous and active as hoped. The success of the intervention is closely linked to the participation of family members, and the lack of constant involvement could have limited the generalisation of the results. Greater active participation by family members could help to consolidate the progress made in therapeutic contexts and facilitate the transfer of the skills acquired to everyday life.

Finally, although the type of measurement used helps monitor changes in the various contexts, it could be integrated with other evaluation methods, such as psychophysiological measurements, which would provide an even more complete picture of the

intervention's impact. Integrating executive functions and emotional regulation skills is important for improving the patient's functioning. Better management of executive functions allows the patient to deal with emotions more effectively, improving their ability to control themselves and their response to stressful situations. An intervention aimed at developing executive functions can, therefore, positively impact self-control and emotional regulation, creating a therapeutic path that strengthens cognitive abilities and promotes an emotional balance that favours greater autonomy and adaptability in everyday situations. The integrated approach between these two areas could represent a key aspect for long-term therapeutic success, with significant repercussions on patients' quality of life and those who assist them.

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